

“In Silico” Seawater

Edoardo Errani^{a,1}, Iván M. Zerón^{a,1}, Miguel A. González^a, Carlos Vega^a, and José L. F. Abascal^{a,2}

^aDepartamento de Química Física, Facultad de Ciencias Químicas, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, 28040 Madrid, Spain

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The heat and mass transport from the equator to the poles, a process called thermohaline circulation, is driven by density gradients of the seawater in oceans. Seawater is essentially an aqueous electrolyte solution. It may seem surprising that, despite that seawater composition is quite complex, most of its physico-chemical properties (and, in particular its density) are essentially determined—in addition to temperature—by salinity. This is because the relative proportions of any two major constituents are always the same and, thus, a single variable—salinity—is representative of seawater composition. In this work we use numerical simulation at a molecular level to evaluate a number of properties relevant to the thermohaline circulation for a system whose composition is close to the average composition of standard seawater. Using a recently proposed forcefield [I.M. Zerón et al., *J. Chem. Phys.* 151, 134504 (2019)] we have computed static, dynamical, structural and interfacial properties of our “in silico” seawater model. Simulation results show a good agreement with experimental measurements for a wide range of temperatures and salinities (up to three times that of the average value in Earth’s oceans).

seawater | molecular simulation | thermohaline circulation

Seawater is a complex solution of substances, mostly ions, in water. The absolute salinity of seawater, S , defined as the total amount of ions (in grams) per kilogram of water(1) is usually between 31 and 38 g/kg. Salinity is a fundamental property of seawater and basic to understanding biological and physical processes in oceans. It is interesting to note that, despite the complexity of the seasalt composition, the most relevant physical properties of marine water (leaving aside surface or coastal effects) depend essentially on a single parameter representing the composition, i.e. the salinity. This is because, irrespective of the total salinity, the relative proportions of any two major constituents are always the same. This evidence is known from the beginning of the nineteenth century(2, 3) and it is sometimes referred to as the Principle of Constant Proportions.

The Principle of Constant Proportions allows to define a precise reference composition for seawater.(4) Along the years it became evident the need of a benchmark for that. In 2008, a Reference Composition—consisting of the proportions of components of Atlantic surface seawater (designed as Standard Seawater)—was defined.(4) Salinity differences are then caused by either evaporating fresh water or adding fresh water from rivers and melted ice. In some way, this allows to consider seawater as two component mixture, seasalt and water, the salinity being the representative variable for the solution concentration.

Temperature of oceans shows a characteristic vertical profile, called thermocline, which depends on the latitude. Similar patterns are found for the salinity, the halocline. Since temperature and salinity determine the physical properties of seawater, density exhibits the same type of vertical profile as the thermocline and halocline. This means that seawater does

not mix vertically. The mixing is produced by ocean currents, as shown for the first time by Sandstrom in 1908.(5) These currents give rise to the thermohaline circulation(6) which plays a primary role on the Earth’s climate(7) and on the marine biology. In this way, knowledge of the dependence of the density on the temperature and salinity of marine water is crucial for the understanding and modellization of the thermohaline circulation.

Numerical simulation(8) has been recognized as a powerful tool to investigate the properties of molecular systems and it is now a widely used technique, complementary to experimental measurements. However, to the best of our knowledge, it has never been used to investigate seawater. There are two likely reasons for that. First, it might seem that the complex seawater composition and its dependence on latitude and depth would prevent an investigation of global interest. However this point of view is unaware of the relative simplicity derived from the principle of constant proportions. Here we show that a system containing a reduced number of ions mimics quite acceptably the mole fractions of seasalt as defined by the seawater Reference Composition and that the resulting system with added water is amenable for computer simulation. On the other hand, molecular simulation relies on the availability of a good force field for the interactions between ions and water. The most abundant ions of seawater are, by large, sodium and chloride. Until recently, studies of sodium chloride aqueous solutions suggested that the available forcefields could not be able to describe quantitatively the seawater properties. The situation has recently changed with the proposal of a force field for NaCl in water(9) based

Significance Statement

Thermohaline circulation plays a fundamental role in regulating the Earth’s climate. It also affects marine resources which provide a significant part of our food intake. Thermohaline circulation is driven by density gradients in oceans. Thus, knowledge of the dependence of the seawater density on temperature and composition is fundamental to model it. The complexity of seawater composition and the limited availability of forcefields have probably prevented the use of molecular simulation to account for the seawater density and other physico-chemical properties. In this work we report the first molecular simulations for seawater. Using a state of the art forcefield and a system representative of the standard seawater composition we provide excellent predictions for static, dynamical, structural and interfacial seawater properties.

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¹E.E. and I.Z. contributed equally to this work.

²To whom correspondence should be addressed. e-mail: abascal@ucm.es

on the widely tested TIP4P/2005(10–12) water model. The success of our work on sodium chloride solutions prompted us to develop a force field, termed as Madrid-2019, including parameters for the more abundant ions of seawater.(13). We are thus in conditions to address the issue of investigating the seawater properties from a molecular perspective.

In this work we study, using molecular simulation with the Madrid-2019 forcefield, the equation of state of seawater, i.e., the dependence of density on temperature and salinity, $\rho = \rho(T, S)$. We also intend to check the performance of the forcefield for other magnitudes representative of the physical behavior of seawater. In particular, we have also evaluated dynamical (viscosity and diffusion coefficients), structural (ionic hydration, ion-ion distribution functions) and interfacial (surface tension) properties. It will be shown that the physical properties of seawater can be satisfactorily predicted by simulations with the Madrid-2019 force field.

1. Modelling seawater

The Reference Composition of Standard Seawater is defined(4) in terms of the mole fractions of the solute components with a precision of $1/10^7$. The number of water molecules required to produce a seawater sample with the Reference Composition and a salinity around 35 g/kg would then be of the order of 5×10^8 . These numbers are obviously not amenable for computer simulation. It is also arguable that very minor components can not affect significantly the physical properties of seawater. One of the goals of this work is just to propose a simplified composition (which we term as “in silico” seasalt, ISSS) that allowing a trustworthy comparison between simulation and experiment.

The first step is to shorten the list of components of seawater. For example, the simulation of a salty solution mimicking as close as possible the seasalt composition but containing just one CO_2 and one OH^- anion would still require around 7×10^7 water molecules. The mole fraction of the six most abundant ions —chloride, sodium, sulfate, magnesium, calcium, and potassium— represent a 99.7 percent of the seawater solute molecules. The addition of two more ions to the list — bicarbonate and bromide— would elevate the percentage to a 99.9%. It is important to note that constituents like dissolved gases (CO_2 , O_2) or inorganic salts (made of phosphorus or nitrogen) may play an essential role in climate regulation of in biological productivity but are completely irrelevant regarding the physical properties. In, fact neither O_2 nor any phosphorus or nitrogen compound take part of the Reference Composition definition of seawater. A solution containing bicarbonate and bromide could indeed be tractable with current computer means. But the interaction potentials for these ions are nowadays much less reliable than those for the most abundant ions. We have thus decided at this stage to describe our “in silico” seasalt by including explicitly only the six ions mentioned above.

From the mole fractions and the ionic charge of the six components mentioned it is possible to calculate the total charge of the sample, which is 0.029. This is related to the fact that most of the neglected constituents carry a negative charge. It is then convenient to include also a especial type of solute by grouping together the mole fraction and charge of the minor components and to assign it a negative charge. Otherwise it would not be possible to satisfy the charge bal-

Table 1. Composition of the seasalt used in this work. Second column shows the mole fractions defined in the Reference Composition for solutes with $x > 0.002$ (4). Third column displays the amounts (g) of each component in the Reference Seawater of $S = 35.16504$ g/kg salinity. Fourth and fifth columns give the number of ions in the ISSS sample and their corresponding mole fractions. The last column presents the amounts (g) of each component in the ISSS+water system at $S = 35.16504$ g/kg .

Component	x_{ion}	mass(S=35)	n_{ISSS}	x_{ISSS}	$m_{ISSS+water}$
Chloride	0.4874839	19.35271	155	0.4874	19.350
Sodium	0.4188071	10.78145	133	0.4182	10.766
Sulfate	0.0252152	2.71235	8	0.0252	2.706
Magnesium	0.0471678	1.28372	15	0.0472	1.284
Calcium	0.0091823	0.41208	3	0.0094	0.423
Potassium	0.0091159	0.39910	3	0.0094	0.413
Minor components	0.0030278	0.22363	1	0.0031	0.215
Sum	1.0000000	35.16504	318	1.0000	35.157

Water	964.83496	15210	964.842
Sum	1000	15528	1000

ance constraint and the relative proportions among the more abundant solutes. It is also convenient to assign to this especial type of ‘ions’ the appropriate molecular mass so that the average atomic weight of the ISSS sample matches that of the Reference Composition, namely 31.4038218 g/mol.(4)

We have carried out a systemic search (see the Supplementary Material) looking for optimal sample sizes that reproduce the Reference Composition as close as possible with a minimum of solute molecules. We have arrived to a relatively small sample containing six types of ions totalising 318 solute molecules. The sample, which will be referred to as ISSS_{318,6}, reproduces the Reference Composition mole fractions with a root mean square deviation around 0.0003. Table1 shows the number of ions of each type of and compares the molality of the components with the corresponding Reference Composition definition. It also shows the amounts of each component in the Reference Composition Standard Seawater and in the ISS+water (318 ions +15210 water molecules) systems at $S = 35.165$ g/kg salinity. In the Supplementary Material we give a detailed description of several optimal compositions for up to 13 seasalt components.

2. Results

In this section we compare the molecular dynamics results for the ISSS+water system with experimental measurements of Standard Seawater. Fig. 1 shows that the calculated densities essentially match the experimental data and its dependence on salinity at 15°C. Notice that the salinity of the more concentrated solution in Fig. 1 is about three times larger than the average salinity of open seas. As to the dependence of the density on temperature we may observe in Fig. 1 that the predictions of the “silico” system are quite accurate for $S=35.16$ g/kg. The simulation results show an excellent performance up to 40°C and the agreement between simulation and experiment degrades slightly at higher temperatures.

The results for the shear viscosity are presented in Figure 2. The simulation data reproduce adequately the dependence of

Fig. 1. a) Top: Density as a function of salinity for seawater at 15°C.; b) Bottom: Density as a function of temperature for seawater at $S=35.16$ g/kg.

Fig. 2. Top: Viscosity as a function of salinity for seawater at $t=15^\circ\text{C}$; Bottom: Viscosity as a function of temperature for seawater at $S=35.16$ g/kg.

160 the viscosity on the salinity though the slope of the curve
 161 (Fig. 2) is a bit steeper than that of the experimental values.
 162 Interestingly, the better agreement is found just for the
 163 more relevant seawater salinities region around 35 g/kg where
 164 experiment and numerical predictions are almost coincident.
 165 Figure 2 shows that the agreement extends to a wide range of
 166 temperatures. It is a fortunate coincidence that in addition
 167 to a general excellent performance of the model, the better
 168 predictions correspond to temperatures and salinities around
 169 the average values of seawater in oceans.

this respect, our simulation results for Mg^{2+} are of particu-
 lar importance because the usual experimental methods for
 the evaluation of D can not be applied to this ion. On the
 other hand, the agreement between experiment and simulation
 gives us some support to inquire the properties at higher
 temperatures where no experimental results have yet been
 reported. It seems that the self-diffusion follow approxi-
 mately an Arrhenius behavior although the lines for the cations
 seem to be slightly bended.

171 Closely related to the viscosity is the diffusivity.

172 **There are no experimental measurements for the self-**
 173 **diffusion of water in seawater (why?).**

174 **Tiene sentido entonces incluir las figuras de D_w ?**

175 **Las ponemos pero en el Supplementary Material?**

176 The self-diffusion coefficient of the water molecules, D_w ,
 177 in seawater of salinity $S = 35.16$ g/kg exhibits an almost per-
 178 fect Arrhenius behavior (see Fig. 3). It is interesting to note
 179 that the ratio between the diffusion coefficient in seawater
 180 and that for pure water at the same temperature seems to
 181 be independent on temperature, $D_w(S)/D_w(0) \approx 0.92$. As
 182 to the dependence of D_w upon salinity, Figure 3 shows that
 183 the diffusion coefficients decrease with the salt concentration.
 184 The deviation from a linear decay is barely appreciable.

We now turn our attention to the structure of the solu-
 tion. The difficulties of separating the contributions of each
 component make extremely difficult to obtain the distribution
 functions from scattering experiments. The role of simulation
 is in this case complementary to experiment.

It is known that the hydration shell of the ions shows a
 scant dependence on salt concentration and to the presence of
 multiple ions in the solution. Our results for seawater confirm
 this assertion. The position of the first extrema of a given
 ion-water rdf is the same, within the statistical uncertainty,
 in solutions at $S = 35.16$ and $S = 98.54$ g/kg. Only the
 height of the peaks are slightly different. Hence, the number of
 waters in the first coordination shell of the ions—the so-called
 hydration numbers, HN— increases marginally with salinity
 (see the Supplementary Material). In fact, the HN results
 are quite similar to those obtained for single salt electrolyte
 solutions at very high concentrations.(13)

Little is known about the residence time, τ , of the water
 molecules around ions. Our results are presented in Figure 5
 (see also the Supplementary Material for the numerical results
 and logarithmic plots showing an exponential decay at short
 times). The order of magnitude of the τ 's is qualitatively

Fig. 3. Top: Self-diffusion coefficient of water as a function of the inverse of the temperature for “in silico” seawater at $S=35.16$ g/kg in logarithmic scale (red circles). The blue symbols represent the ratio between the simulation values of the diffusion coefficients in seawater and those in simulations of pure water at the same temperature. Bottom: Self-diffusion coefficients of water as a function of salinity for seawater at 15°C . Lines are a polynomial fit, quadratic for D_w and linear for $D_w(S)/D_w(0)$.

Fig. 4. Self-diffusion coefficients of cations (top) and anions (bottom) as a function of temperature for seawater at $S=35.16$ g/kg. Small symbols are the simulation results and large symbols are the experimental data. (14, 15) Lines are a guide to the eye linking the numerical results.

distribution functions —i.e., location and height of the maxima and minima— are essentially the same as those of the single salt aqueous solution at similar concentrations.

The situation may be different when dealing with less abundant species, especially when these are divalent ions. Let us consider the magnesium-sulfate distribution function.

In Figure 6 we compare the Mg-S distribution function in seawater at $S=35.1$ g/kg with that of a solution containing only magnesium and sulfate ions at the same concentration (though, since magnesiums outnumber sulfates in seawater, some chloride anions must be added to enforce the charge balance). As seen in the plot the value of the Mg-S distribution function of the latter solution almost doubles that for seawater along a considerable range of distances. Only at separations around 2 nm both curves cross and the coordination numbers of both solutions converge. This seems to be due to a shielding effect: the divalent ions attract unlike charged ions and, since the monovalent sodium and chloride ions are much more abundant, some of them surround the divalent ions thus reducing their effective charge.

Figure 7 shows the increase in the surface tension of “in silico” seawater respect to that of pure (TIP4P/2005) water as a function of salinity at 15°C and 80°C . The agreement with experimental results is excellent at oceanographic conditions. Besides, the variation with salinity is almost quantitatively predicted at 15°C . As to the 80°C , the agreement is only qual-

222 similar to those of a previous report. (16) Quantitative differences are observed not only because of the use of different
 223 forcefields but also dues to the reduced simulation lengths in
 224 the Koneshan et al. paper. The residence times are longer for
 225 the smaller ions. Since divalent cations are very small, waters
 226 around them are very tightly binded. In fact, the lifetime
 227 of waters around magnesium ions is much longer than our
 228 simulation length so we may only estimate it by a fit of the
 229 autocorrelation function to an exponential decay. For cations
 230 carrying the same electronic charge, the ionic size increases
 231 with the atomic number so the values of τ for calcium and
 232 potassium are smaller than those for magnesium and sodium,
 233 respectively. As expected, anions exhibit a looser hydration
 234 layer than cations. The large size of the sulfate anion moti-
 235 vates that, despite being a divalent ion, the lifetime of waters
 236 around sulfates is quite similar to that of chlorides. Finally,
 237 it is worth to mention that the effect of a significant increase
 238 of the seawater salinity (by a factor of about three) is a small
 239 increase of the residence times, less than a 10% (see the Sup-
 240 plementary Material).

242 Given the complexity of the seawater composition, the
 243 number of radial distribution functions (rdf) is quite large
 244 so we only summarize here the more significant results. The
 245 presence of other ions, even if some of them are divalent, does
 246 not affect much the sodium-chloride rdf's. We show in the
 247 Supplementary Material that the main features of the Na-Cl

Fig. 5. Residence times of water molecules in the hydration shell of the ions in seawater at 15°C for two different salinities. Top panel: cations; bottom panel: anions. Solid lines are the results at $S=35.16$ g/kg and dashed lines correspond to $S=98.53$ g/kg. The time axis is represented in logarithmic scale in order to get a better appreciation of the behavior at short and long times for all the ions in the same plot.

Fig. 6. Mg-S radial distribution and running coordination numbers for two solutions at 15°C with the same number of water molecules, magnesium and sulfate ions (15210, 18 and 8 respectively). One of the systems is the ISSS+water solution at $S=35.16$ g/kg and, thus, sodium, chloride, calcium and potassium ions are present in the solution. The other system does not contain those ions with the exception of 20 chloride anions required to constrain the charge balance. The coordination number refers to the average number of magnesium cations in the first coordination shell of a sulfate.

itative. The results follow the experimental trend but the slope gradient of the dependence on salinity is somewhat low, approximately 3/4 of the experimental value for $\gamma(S) - \gamma(0)$.

Fig. 7. Surface tension of seawater relative to that of pure water. Symbols are the results for "in silico" seawater using TIP4P/2005 water as a reference; lines are experimental data (17, 18). Results at 80°C have been shifted 2 mN/m for clarity.

Before concluding this section we would like to answer two important questions. The first one is to know whether the excellent performance of the Madrid-2019 is extensive to other force fields. In the Supplementary Material we show that the answer is clearly negative. On the other hand, one may wonder if the use of a more detailed representation of the seasalt composition might affect the quality of the results of this work. At this moment we can not assess directly this point because there are no available parameters for other solutes compatible with those of the Madrid-2019 force field. However we may get reasonable suggestions. In the Supplementary Material we show a comparison of some of the results for the ISSS composition and those obtained by replacing the calcium and potassium ions by magnesium and sodium. There we demonstrate that a system made of the four more abundant ions already captures essentially the physico-chemical behavior of seawater and that the explicit incorporation of the calcium and potassium ions produces marginal changes in the results. Further increase of the composition details beyond that used in this work would only be strictly necessary if one intends to know specific properties associated to a certain ion not included in the ISSS sample.

3. Conclusions and final discussion

Probably, the most important conclusion of this work is simply that the molecular simulation of seawater is within our reach. We have shown that molecular dynamics simulations using a state of the art force field is able to produce results in excellent agreement with experimental data. It is difficult to assess at this moment the importance of this fact. We recall that the outcome of the simulation is not only a wide set of macroscopic properties but that it also gives detailed microscopic information which is sometimes very difficult to be obtained in experiments. In this work we have calculated relevant magnitudes for which there is a large set of experimental determinations. It is the case of the density, viscosity or surface tension. The quality of the predictions validate the

forcefield employed and our simplified representation of the seawater composition. This gives support to the predictions for structural quantities such as the hydration numbers and residence times of water molecules around ions as well as the ion-ion distribution functions. We have also obtained reliable results for the ionic diffusivity, a magnitude for which the experimental data are extremely scarce.

Once the force field has been verified, molecular simulation also allows to carry out “what if?” pseudo experiments. One may investigate the effect of small changes in composition by modifying the amount of any constituent. In fact, we have reported in this work the effect of replacing the calcium and potassium ions by sodiums and magnesium, respectively. Although we have limited our study to a seasalt containing only six ions, nothing disables, in principle, to extend our investigations to a more detailed composition. For instance, it would be very interesting to learn something about the behavior of minor, though very relevant, components such as the (bi)carbonate anions and the neutral molecule carbon dioxide. The main problem, apart of an affordable increase in the computational cost, is the availability of reliable force fields for these species. The design of appropriate force fields for them is not a trivial task but it is nowadays at our hands. In fact, we hope that this study will stimulate work in that direction.

Materials and Methods

In this work we study, we use molecular dynamics simulation to investigate the properties of a system mimicking the composition of Standard Seawater. We have chosen the successful TIP4P/2005 model(19) to account for the interactions between the water molecules. For the ion-ion and ion-water interactions we have used a recent parametrization(13) —the so-called Madrid-2019 forcefield— which gives an excellent performance for several aqueous solutions including all the ionic species present in our ‘In silico’ seawater model. Most of the systems are made of 15210 water molecules and the number of ions are multiples of the ISSS sample shown in Table 1. We have also studied a system at a lower salinity by considering the 318 ion of the ISS sample and increasing the number of water molecules to 30420.

The simulations have been performed using GROMACS 4.5.5(20) with a 2 fs timestep. The cut-off radii have been set to 0.95 nm for both electrostatic and Lennard-Jones interactions. Long range corrections to the Lennard-Jones potential energy and pressure were included. Long range electrostatic interactions have been evaluated with the smooth Particle Mesh Ewald method.(21) The geometry of the water molecules and of the sulfate ions has been enforced using *ad hoc* constraints, in particular, the SHAKE algorithm.(22) The Nosé-Hoover thermostat(23, 24) has been applied to set the temperatures at the desired values. All the simulations in the isobaric-isothermal (NpT) ensemble were performed at a fixed pressure of 1 bar by means of an isotropic Parrinello-Rahman barostat.(25) The average volumes obtained in the NpT runs were used as input for the simulations at constant volume performed to evaluate the viscosities. The simulated time of the runs has been typically 10 ns for the calculation of the water-ions structure and residence times, and 100 ns for the evaluation of viscosities, surface tension, ion-ion diffusivities and ion-ion rdf’s. Exceptionally a run of 500 ns has been carried out for the state at 15°C, $S=35.16$ g/kg in order to increase the accuracy of the diffusivity of the minor components.

The evaluation of several properties such as the density or the radial distribution function from a molecular dynamics run is trivial and may be found in textbooks.(8) However, the determination of other quantities still require some methodological comments. For the evaluation of the viscosity we have used the Green-Kubo formula

$$\eta = \frac{V}{kT} \int_0^\infty \langle P_{\alpha\beta}(t_0) P_{\alpha\beta}(t_0+t) \rangle_{t_0} dt. \quad [1]$$

where $P_{\alpha\beta}(t)$ is a component of the pressure tensor. Some care is needed (see Ref. 26 for details) to select the upper limit and the asymptotic behavior of the integral. The self-diffusion coefficients have been evaluated by means of the Einstein relation

$$D = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{6t} \langle [r_i(t) - r_i(t_0)]^2 \rangle, \quad [2]$$

where $r_i(t)$ and $r_i(t_0)$ are the positions of the i -th particle at time t and a certain origin of time t_0 . For the calculation of the surface tension γ we considered a slab of liquid placed between two empty regions. In the case of a planar interface, γ is evaluated as

$$\gamma = \frac{L_z}{2} (\bar{p}_N - \bar{p}_T), \quad [3]$$

where \bar{p}_N and \bar{p}_T are the macroscopic normal and tangencial components of the pressure tensor.

It is well known that the truncation of the potential affects significantly the interfacial properties.(27) For the calculation of γ we have extended the cut-off radii r_c . We have performed two sets of calculations using $r_c = 1.3$ nm and $r_c = 1.7$ nm and checked that the difference between the surface tension at a given salinity with respect to that for pure water $\gamma(S)-\gamma(0)$ is independent of the cut-off radii. The self-diffusion coefficients are also quite sensitive to finite-size effects but the size of our samples is already large enough to avoid this problem. In addition, it is expected that the error should cancel when we compare two vales at identical condirions. Thus, $D(S)/D(0)$ is a more appropriate magnitude to investigate the diffusivity in seawater than $D(S)$ alone.

The hydration numbers, HN, are the average number of water molecules in the first solvation shell of an ion and are trivially obtained by integrating the corresponding water-ion rdf’s. The residence times of these water molecules may be calculated from time correlation functions(16) defined by

$$R(t) = \frac{1}{N_h} \sum_{i=1}^{N_h} \langle \Theta_i(0) \Theta_i(t) \rangle, \quad [4]$$

which allow to determinate an average lifetime, τ , defined as

$$\tau = \int_0^\infty \langle R(t) \rangle dt. \quad [5]$$

Typically, $R(t)$ exhibits an exponential decay at short times, $R(t) \propto \exp(-t/\tau)$ so it can also be estimated from the corresponding fit.

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